

"Pretty Vicious Abuse" - Structural Analysis of Organised Homophobic Hate Speech Against an Irish Minister on Twitter

SEX PAN!CS Conference
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Context: Roderic O'Gorman TD

- O'Gorman is a member of parliament (TD) elected for the first time in February 2020, and a member of government - the incumbent ***Minister for Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth***, since June 2020.
- O'Gorman is an openly gay politician, who succeeded another openly gay ***Minister for Children and Youth Affairs***, Katherine Zappone (in office 2016-2020).
- In mid-March 2023, O'Gorman publicly discussed the nature and extent of online abuse he is subject to, on national television. (*The Week in Politics, 11 March 2023*)

Image: O'Gorman in 2022, Houses of the Oireachtas CC 2.0

Context: March 2023 Incident

A prior national main evening new broadcast (*RTE*) had been interrupted by a protestor who described O'Gorman as a **"child groomer"**

"The kind of the abuse that I get is very much focused on being gay ... Every politician has to be ready for robust criticism, absolutely, but there is a definite change in dialogue in certain parts of the public on these particular issues"

O'Gorman, The Week in Politics, 11 March 2023

Context: Twitter and this study

- The initial intent of this work was to explore this perceived *change in the dialogue* by compiling and structurally examining a corpus of @-replies made in response to all 2023 tweets from @rodericogorman, as well as some related sources.
- Such Twitter data provides a conversationally-structured set of responses which can be examined: **who** - *the interacting accounts*; **how** - *the language and images being used*; **why** - *the apparent themes and motivations within responses*; **when** - *whether certain content triggers certain responses*.
- The work of Zizi Papacharissi on *affective publics* (2014) and Sara Ahmed on the *cultural politics of emotion* (2004, etc.), as well as work on *Twitter-specific publics* (Axel Bruns, Jean Burgess, Bartlett et al., etc.) provide frameworks for analysis of the network and interactions in this dataset.
- Comparison is possible with previous corpora of specific Irish public political discourse on Twitter, in studies which collected or discussed this (*e.g. Mulligan 2016, Hunt 2019, Reidy & Suiter 2023*)

Context: How this study changed

- This research was prompted by O'Gorman's discussion in mid-March, and described (*and titled!*) at a time before two important changes occurred, which are worth mentioning for their effect on the research design and interpretation:
 1. O'Gorman (and his team) altered his usage of Twitter to **restrict replies** to those the account follows on all posts made since ~01 April 2023.
 2. **Various changes have been made to Twitter as a platform**, deriving from Elon Musk's ownership of it (*since 27 October 2022*), radically altering participation and discussion there

Context: Restricted Replies

Replies were restricted on posts from *@rodericogorman* from **~01 April 2023**, following the year's most replied-to post.

"After discussing with my team, we concluded that the amount - and vitriolic nature - of comments that followed my tweets - and others social media posts - was so excessive that we no longer wanted to provide a location for such comments."

O'Gorman, Interview, 11 October 2023

A screenshot of a tweet from Roderic O'Gorman TD (@rodericogorman) posted on March 31, 2023, at 5:00 PM. The tweet has 184.8K views, 881 replies, 138 retweets, and 594 likes. The text of the tweet reads: "Solidarity with every trans person who has experienced violence, harassment, online abuse - and who has had to listen to the frequent and downright shameful dog whistles issued by those who should know better. 🏳️‍🌈" Below the text, it says "No LGB without the T." and "#TransDayOfVisibility". The reply count of 881 is highlighted with a red box.

Source: Twitter/X <https://twitter.com/rodericogorman/status/1641832872771289090>

Context: Changes to Twitter / X

- Elon Musk's purchase of Twitter, and his ownership active from 27 October 2022, has radically altered the platform in terms of affordances, usage norms, participation levels, and utility as a site of research.
 - ➔ Specifically, the dismantling of content moderation and regulatory compliance frameworks, the firing of large numbers of staff, and the alterations to the ranking algorithm for posts have substantially affected how the platform is *experienced by users*
 - ➔ *The extent of change to usage patterns is difficult to determine.* For Ireland (with a previous top-5 per-capita-active-use in the mid-2010s), overall usage of the platform and frequency of posting seem to have fallen sharply through late 2022 and Q1/2023 (*IPSOS*), though apparently without significant account deletion.
 - ➔ The removal or alteration of terms for many elements of the Twitter API has altered researchers' ability to gather the datasets that historically made it a key site for social media research.

Findings: Overview of the data

- The set of tweets from *@rodericogorman* from 01 January to 01 October 2023 comprises **316** tweets.
- From 01 April 2023, replies are restricted, so the set of tweets from which replies were collected are those in January, February, and March. There are **94** tweets in this period, but they yield **6277 replies**.
48 are posts; 37 are retweets; 9 are quote-tweets.

➔ Certain topics resulted in disproportionate numbers of replies:

➔ *Note that replies are frequently not related to topic, when the topic is constituency or childcare, or when the tweet immediately follows a previously highly commented one.*

Tweets	Topic	Replies
23	Constituency Related	699
26	Childcare & Children's Rights	848
9	Refugees, Migrants & Integration	1320
6	LGBT Issues	1397
3	Gender	1146

Findings: Other most-replied-to tweets

2 Topic: **Racism**
Replies: **429**

@rodericogorman

The Government has today launched its National Action Plan Against Racism.

Ireland has gone 15 years without a specific plan to combat racism.

This Plan has been long-awaited, and its effective implementation will be key to making Ireland a safer, and more inclusive country.

0:06

8:02 PM · Mar 21, 2023 · **92.2K** Views

429 71 142 5

3 Topic: **Gender**
Replies: **392**

@rodericogorman

Privileged to represent Ireland again at the @UN_CSW Commission on the Status of Women; the most important annual global forum dedicated to advancing gender equality #CSW67 @irishmissionun

0:01 / 0:45

5:50 PM · Mar 6, 2023 from Dublin City, Ireland · **88K** Views

392 59 49 2

4 Topic: **Gender**
Replies: **388**

@rodericogorman

In many parts of the world, hard-won progress on the rights of women & girls is being rolled back.

Today I spoke at the UN Security Council to reaffirm Ireland’s commitment to gender equality nationally & globally. #CSW67 @irishmissionun

ALT

8:01 PM · Mar 7, 2023 · **65.2K** Views

Findings: Language used

- Examining word frequency (*and adjusting for more common but less meaningful words e.g not, like, with, etc.*), the most frequent words recurring in the text of replies to @rodericogorman in Q1/2023 are respectively:
 - ➔ **resign** - often the only word in single-word replies; *possibly common to any Minister and thus unremarkable, but I don't have a good comparison*
 - ➔ **racism/racist** - almost always in reference to either not being racist or to being "*racist against the Irish*" or "*anti-white racism*", etc.
 - ➔ **women/woman** - overwhelmingly arising from requests to "*define a woman*" or to discourse related to how trans rights oppress women, etc.
 - ➔ **children** - perhaps unsurprising for the *Minister for Children*, but frequently in contexts questioning his fitness to be around children
 - ➔ **groomer** - including the formulation **o'groomer**, referring to his name (*and to a low level of imagination*)
 - ➔ **irish** - again unsurprising in overall context but frequently a component of racist speech

Findings: Language used

The fifth most frequently-occurring meaningful word, *groomer*, relates to pedophilia and is part of a wider recurrence of these references:

 [Redacted] · Mar 22
Groomer and peadophile supporter wants to talk about racism 🤔

🗨️ ↻️ ❤️ 📊 7 ↗️

 [Redacted] · Jan 4
I wouldn't let him near any kids ... 🚫

🗨️ ↻️ ❤️ 6 📊 49 ↗️

 [Redacted] · Mar 30
U are pos , grooming cunt

🗨️ ↻️ 1 ❤️ 1 📊 31 ↗️

 [Redacted] · Mar 8
Youre a closeted peter file groomers

🗨️ ↻️ ❤️ 📊 4 ↗️

 [Redacted] · Mar 30
Paedo enabler

🗨️ ↻️ 1 ❤️ 13 📊 96 ↗️

 [Redacted] · Mar 6
O groomer you need to [#resign](#). It's morally wrong and sick what you want thought in school, leave our children alone they aren't part of your sick trans ideology

🗨️ 3 ↻️ 2 ❤️ 62 📊 491 ↗️

 [Redacted] · Mar 22
Can we get a law where anyone who associated with known paedophile apologists is barred from having anything to do with children ?

🗨️ 1 ↻️ 2 ❤️ 105 📊 799 ↗️

 [Redacted] · Mar 7
Stay out of or schools and away from our children Roderic.

Findings: User profiles

- The 6277 replies derive from **558 users**. (*One off these is @rodericogorman, who adds 103 threaded replies across various tweets*)
- This gives an average reply-per-user of ~11 tweets, *but this is misleading*. Many users only post one reply in the dataset, and a small number of users account for a large proportion of the replies, due to repeated presence.
 - **The top 20 users by frequency account for >21% of the replies** (1336).
- Examining the users overall, there is a clear increase over Q1/2023 in **suspicious accounts** (*by Twitter norms: no image, no followers/following, no posts - just replies or retweets, username with numbers, etc.*). In almost all cases of manually examining these, these appear to be human users.
- Among the top 20 replying users, several repeat images and text (*esp. "groomer" and "resign"*) and the majority include the Irish flag emoji in their name.
 - These users **all** post, retweet, and reply on other topics, mainly political and frequently referring to US politics - often trans-related content, racist rhetoric, and news regarding migrants (*esp. crime*).

Findings: Links to alt-right sources

- All images in the replies were collated, examined for frequency of any which recur (*especially from separate users*), and checked for potential origin via Google reverse image searches.
- A surprising finding was the extent of re-publication of memes and images - often unrelated to the tweet topic - which **derive from US sources, especially alt-right subreddits**. (*These may pre-date their appearance on reddit, from prior postings in closed platforms such as 8chan, etc.*)
- Similarly, textual references in some replies occasionally made direct reference to US political contexts (e.g. **Trump, Biden, "dems", "woke democrats"**, etc.) linking the conceptual framing by these posters with the US.
 - *Note that while some component of these may be bots, the vast majority are references from users whose other postings on Twitter demonstrate realistically human interaction and specific knowledge of Irish contexts also*

Findings: Examples of memes & images

WARNING: Several of these are going to be terrible.

This image content is included in 2023 replies to @rodericogorman, though deleted later in some but not all cases, as evidenced in October 2023 checks against the original dataset.

These images appeared frequently, but not exclusively in replies to posts about refugees, racism, migrants, or integration.

All exist in prior US alt-right contexts

Findings: Examples of memes & images

This image content is included in 2023 replies to @rodericogorman, though deleted later in some but not all cases, as evidenced in October 2023 checks against the original dataset.

Anti-LGBT images deriving from US contexts.

Findings: Examples of memes & images

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Recurring images which feature O'Gorman directly.

Findings: Repeated themes of child-danger

- The most-often-included image in replies to @rodericogorman is one depicting him at the 2018 Dublin Pride parade with Australian-British activist **Peter Tatchell**, and is used explicitly or implicitly suggest that O'Gorman supports pedophilia, based on remarks made by Tatchell about age of consent in 1997.
 - Following Twitter commentary on the photograph in 2020, the allegation was taken up by The National Party and others, including at a protest outside the Oireachtas in July 2020.
 - O'Gorman and Tatchell issues statements unambiguously rejecting the assertions.
- Similarly, images or references in text to O'Gorman's **supposed promotion of "minor attracted person" pornography**, or to his **supposed satanism or cannibalism of children** are both present and both derive from prior theories which started online and have been repeatedly debunked (*e.g. TheJournal FACTCHECK, August 2020*)

Findings: Repeated themes of child-danger

These images appear (and are referenced in) replies frequently.
The Tatchell image (including cropped variants) appears 68 times.

Conclusions

- O'Gorman is correct about the changed nature of the discourse on Twitter, both in terms of content and participation.
 - ➔ His tweets averaged **4.89 replies across 2022**, but **66.77 replies in Q1/2023** (until replies were deactivated).
 - ➔ Replies to him in 2023 feature **a consistent theme of referencing pedophilia** (average of 6% of replies to any tweet; 12-15% of replies in most responded to tweets).
 - ➔ **Replies from suspicious accounts rise over Q1/2023** (numbered usernames, no followers, reply-only) - accounting for for ~5% of replies in late March tweets
 - ➔ **Replies almost entirely lack threaded structure** - i.e. are not conversational discourse, but one-off responses; compare this to 2015 and 2018 discourses on marriage or abortion referendums where >30% of replies to Irish politicians are threaded conversations of multiple respondents
 - ➔ Replies include (and persist for longer with) **broad and often topic-irrelevant hate-speech or images** (esp. memes deriving from alt-right sources and US contexts).

Conclusions

- **There is a persistent component of the reply content to O'Gorman, rising over early 2023, that is overtly homophobic and seeks to incite or persist in creating moral panic about his fitness to be near children.**
 - ➔ Text and image content unambiguously links O'Gorman to pedophilia, child endangerment, and supposed agenda-pushing, all related to his homosexuality.
 - ➔ We can understand a participating cohort as an affective public, motivated by exaggerated hatred and performative protection-based rationales for it: *They are not racist, but protecting Irishness; not homophobic, but protecting children, etc.*
- **A likely contributor to the state of discourse - including the participants within it and the nature of persisting overt hate-speech content - is the alterations made to Twitter's operation in late 2022, after Musk's ownership began**
 - ➔ In mid-December 2022, Musk disbanded Twitter's *Trust & Safety Council*, and fired large numbers of staff involved in moderation, monitoring, and compliance with regulation
 - ➔ Later (and extant) changes to the Twitter algorithm have altered the prominence of hate-speech and made previously fringe content visible and present

Conclusions

- **Sadly, it's probably not going to get any better for political discourse on Twitter / X.**
Its golden era - such as it was - seems firmly over.

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